

22NRM03 MetHyTrucks

D3 - Report on the development of four reference methods/systems including implementation of sampling systems for hydrogen quality assessment

Organisation name of the lead participant for the deliverable: SINTEF

Other partners: ENGIE, NPL, ZBT, RISE

Due date of the deliverable: June 2025

Actual submission date of the deliverable: 8th January 2026

Confidentiality Status: PU - Public, fully open (remember to deposit public deliverables in a trusted repository)

Deliverable Cover Sheet

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The project has received funding from the European Partnership on Metrology, co-financed from the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme and by the Participating States.

European Partnership Co-funded by the European Union

**METROLOGY
PARTNERSHIP**

Glossary

HD: Heavy-duty

LD: Light-duty

HRS: Hydrogen Refuelling Station

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1 Summary

The deliverable describes summarily the hydrogen sampling strategies which have been developed in the tasks 2.1 (gaseous species) and 2.2 (particulates) of the project MetHyTrucks and the steps needed to implement these devices onsite (task 2.3). The report also shows the successful implementation of these devices at two different stations: at the ZBT station in Duisburg, Germany, October 2024 and at the Tyseley Refuelling Hub, UK in September 2025.

In this report, we consider only the implementation i.e. assessing the functionality of the sampling systems at a HD-HRS and compliance with the refuelling protocols and other HRS parameters.

2 Introduction

Hydrogen can significantly contribute to reducing emissions from the transportation sector as it is particularly well suited as a fuel for long-haul heavy-duty (HD) vehicles. A recent report from Hydrogen Europe [1] gauged industry's commitments and predictions for the development of hydrogen in the whole transport sector and highlighted a certain degree of confidence that hydrogen-based technologies will scale up and be widely used in all applications and market segments if the proper preconditions are met.

Hydrogen-powered vehicles require extremely pure hydrogen as some contaminants can reduce the performance of the fuel cell even at very low levels. The purity of the hydrogen dispensed at hydrogen refuelling points should comply with the technical specifications included in the ISO 14687 [2], EN 17124 [3], and SAE J2719:202003 [4] standards. The quality of the hydrogen can be controlled either onsite using online monitoring or after spot sampling and transport to a laboratory for offline analysis [5] [6].

The uptake of hydrogen for heavy-duty transport requires further standardisation to support Europe's green energy future. Sampling systems and methods have already been developed for use at hydrogen refuelling stations (HRS) for light-duty (LD) vehicles, however there is a lack of technical evidence for heavy-duty transport.

The project MetHyTrucks has adapted existing, and developed new, sampling systems for HD applications. This is the first step needed to enable the collection of a representative sample of hydrogen at these emerging stations. Once a sampling system is developed and tested for function, it must be controlled that it can be implemented at any given station. This exercise consists of choosing a test station and carefully planning for the implementation of the sampling device onsite.

The goal of this deliverable is to describe summarily the hydrogen sampling strategies which have been developed in the task 2.1 and 2.2 of the project MetHyTrucks and to describe the steps needed to implement these devices onsite (task 2.3).

2.1 Sampling systems developed for the gaseous species

2.1.1 ENGIE sampling device

ENGIE has developed a device adaptable for stations delivering hydrogen fuel both at 350 and 700 bar and which also allows to perform online analysis of oxygen and water during a refuelling event. Contrary to the other "gas serial methods", this method doesn't require the overriding of the safety protocol of the station. The ENGIE device has been fitted with a receptacle able to plug 350 barg HDV nozzle. The device was originally designed and qualified to support pressure up to 875 barg. The tank volume of the ENGIE's device of 55L and the valves could also originally support flow rates up to 120g/s.

As the smallest tank volume implemented in the table of the HDV 350 barg HF filling protocols (CEP/WENGER) is around 835 liter, the current volume of the tank does not allow the station to deliver hydrogen without by-passing the safety protocol. New protocols are in preparation and will, maybe, include tank volume around 420L. To be able to sample without by-passing the safety protocol, the volume of tank must be increased and

to that effect, the whole bench must be redesigned in order to get enough space to fit this much bigger tank. Sampling device and tank is designed to be used from -40 to $+80^{\circ}\text{C}$. The sampling protocol needs to ensure that the temperature of hydrogen will be between these limits.

ENGIE brings his own venting mast on-site for the sampling. It consists on a stainless steel mast of 3 m height connected to the sampling device through a 10 m stainless steel flexible hose. This solution allows to safely vent hydrogen contained into the tank after the sampling. The tank is PED (pressure equipment directive) certified and need to be inerted before transport. This step could be eliminated by using instead a TPED (transport pressure equipment directive) tank.

Figure 1 – Engie device

2.1.2 HySaM sampling device

The HySaM device has originally been developed to sample from 700 bar refuelling stations. In conformity to SAE, it is pressure rated for 875 bar. The system is divided into three modules. Module 1 contains all parts for simultaneously sampling up to three cylinders (2.25 or 10 l). Module 2 is the mobile vent. Module 3 contains a buffer tank including the necessary safety components. By using module 2, sampling can be performed without refuelling a FCEV. Optionally, the vent lines (including safety relief valves) from modules 1 and 3 can be connected to module 2 or to the HRS vent line. Also optional is the simultaneous sampling for particles. To adapt the system to HD-HRS, a new line will be added for sampling at 350 bar. The 350 bar hardware is suitable for minimal hydrogen temperatures of -20°C . With the new design, it will be possible to sample from 700 bar and 350 bar refuelling lines.

A receptacle has been added to the HySaM device to accommodate sampling at HD HRS (350 bar). The sizes of the piping have also been increased to support high flow (up to 120 g/s). An added switch valve can be used to direct the gas into the correct pressure line (350 or 700 bar). While performing a parallel sampling (e.g. with a FCEV), the new device is compatible with all protocols for HD up to 120 g/s. The device does not need to be modified for the venting operations.

Figure 2 - The HySaM device

Within the project “Comparability of Hydrogen Quality Analytics” (RingWaBe), which is funded by the German Federal Ministry for Digital and Transport (BMDV), the HySaM system was further developed and tested. The project partners - Deutsches Zentrum für Luft- und Raumfahrt (DLR), DVGW-Forschungsstelle am Engler-Bunte-Institut des Karlsruher Instituts für Technologie (EBI), Open Grid Europe GmbH (OGE), Zentrum für Sonnenenergie- und Wasserstoff-Forschung Baden-Württemberg (ZSW), and Zentrum für BrennstoffzellenTechnik GmbH (ZBT) - conducted round-robin tests in which samplings were conducted with their respective devices at identical refuelling points in order to validate the comparability of the sampling procedure regarding hydrogen quality. For this purpose, two sampling events were carried out at an HRS in Gießen (30 September 2024 and 3 December 2024) and one in Duisburg at the ZBT’s hydrogen testfield (4 June 2025).

Within the MetroHyVe2 project, a comparison of sampling systems from NPL, Engie, Air Liquide, and ZBT (legacy HySaM) was conducted on 19 October 2022. For testing purposes, ZBT received the new HySaM at the end of 2023 and conducted an initial test refuelling using the 35 MPa HF nozzle on December 21, 2023. Thus, the sampling event with the new HySaM within the MetHyTrucks project took place during the validation period, and no prior comparison with the systems from Engie and NPL had been conducted.

2.1.3 NPL DirSam (ASTM D7606-7) method and NPL HD-ParSam (Heavy duty hydrogen parallel sampling)

Within a NPL internal project, two new sampling systems have been developed for HD applications. The systems NPL DirSam and NPL HD-ParSam are designed for heavy duty sampling and therefore planned to operate up to 120 g/s, pressure up to 350 bar for heavy duty. The two systems are compatible with 700 bar HRS light duty (up to 60 g/s).

The NPL DirSAM follows a direct sampling strategy as described in the standard ASTM D7606-17 [7]. As any direct sampling system, it requires the HRS to be in maintenance mode, operated by HRS technician to deliver pressure and flow. The sampling is performed at the nozzle and the venting of hydrogen into the atmosphere

is performed through an exhaust stack. The sampling device is detailed in Figure 3. The HRS nozzle is connected to the sampler through high flow (HF) receptacle 1, indicated as RP1, with part number TN1 H₂ HF (WEH, Illertissen, Bayern, Germany). The pressure of the gas is reduced from the HRS input pressure down to 100 bar by a regulator (TESCOM, Skelmersdale, UK). Then, a pressure relief valve (PRV) is present, with relief pressure of 175 bar to ensure safety of the system (sampling cylinder operating pressure is approximately 200 bar). The gas can then be vented through a portable vent, sampled into a 10 L sampling cylinder with single ended valve or with a double-ended DIN 477 no. 1 valve. The use of double ended valve allow to flow through the cylinder to a portable vent. An important step is to purge and condition the sampling system which is realised through several purges. The NPL DirSAM is adaptable for stations delivering hydrogen fuel both at 350 and 700 bar and is capable of up to 120 g/s (high flow). It comes with a 5 meters flexible line connected to a tripod foot. The flow to the cylinders is adjustable using a flow metering valve. The cylinder for sampling is a 10 L aluminum cylinder with DIN 477/1 valve. NPL DirSAM has been compared for light duty application to various sampling systems (H₂ Qualitizer [8], HySAM, ENGIE and Air Liquide sampling systems) in project MetroHyVe 2 or HyQuality EU.

Figure 3 - (a) Schematic of the hydrogen fuel sampling system using a direct sampling strategy used by the National Physical Laboratory (NPL) and referred to as NPL DirSAM. (b) Image of the NPL DirSAM sampling system (Enakonda et al. [8]).

The second system NPL ParSAM follows a parallel sampling strategy. It allows sampling according to the ISO19880-9 [9] without overriding the refuelling protocol. The NPL ParSAM is following similar strategy as HySAM or H₂ Qualitizer however it incorporates exchangeable nozzle and receptacle to enable with the same kit 700 bar light duty HRS sampling and 350 bar heavy duty sampling. The sampling is realised using a tee on the flow path going from the HRS to the FCEV. The pressure is reduced and flow restricted to allow control fill of the cylinder. It also offers the possibility of purging and venting to the atmosphere with its own sampling vent. The method is adaptable for stations delivering hydrogen fuel both at 350 and 700 bar and is capable of up to 120 g/s.

2.2 Sampling systems developed for the particulates

2.2.1 HYDAC PSA-H70 and PSA-H70 MC2

The PSA-H70 is a high-pressure filter holder designed to be placed in series between an HRS nozzle and the receptacle of an FCEV or a simulated tank system used as sink. The system is constructed for 70 MPa and follow a regular fuelling protocol, so that no manual override of the HRS is required. To protect the filter from the initial test pulse of 87.5 MPa a rotary valve is installed upstream the filter to limit the pressure exerted on the filter. After the test pulse, the valve is put in a fully open position allowing for the full flow and pressure over the filter required for representative sampling. The system is depressurized with a bleed valve before disconnection from HRS and FCEV is done. The adapter is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4 - HYDAC PSA-H70 sampling adapter.

In a MCP 02 version of the PSA-H70 released in 2018, the design was changed to remove the rotary and bleed valves. The rotary valve removal implies that filter substrate support needs to be replaced more frequently. The bleed valve was replaced by a feedback loop with check valves, allowing depressurization through the nozzle. After discussions with providers of particulates sampling devices, a challenge has been identified (lack of hardware to measure particulate at high flow conditions required for HD). The plan is therefore to work at up to 60 g/s (as it is available today) which is in the lower range of the HD conditions still goes beyond the state-of-art as it should show the effect of higher flows than the ones used at LD HRS as planned

3 Implementation of the systems

The implementation of any sampling device requires a careful planning which includes technical aspects (such as the steps needed to connect the sampling device to the station and the compliance with the HRS parameters that fit the sampling system and the requirement of the sampling - pressure, flow, temperature, protocol, storage banks), safety concerns (such as vent requirement and risk assessment), and time planning (the sampling exercise is not part of the normal procedure that occurs at a HRS. This downtime has to be minimised to reduce the impact on the refuelling of trucks).

3.1 Implementation of the systems at the ZBT station in Duisburg

The hydrogen testing field, located in Duisburg, Germany, was developed 2017. The platform has a hydrogen capacity of approximately 500 kg hydrogen stored at 200, 500 and 900 bar. Hydrogen can be dispensed at 350 or 700 bar and several protocols can be applied (SAE J2601, MC formular, PRHYDE & free configurable). This station was chosen for different reasons, first the accessibility as it belongs to one of the partners of the project, the fact that this station has been used in previous projects, and as the hydrogen dispensed there is known to contain measurable levels of impurities which is useful for the validation and/or comparison of sampling systems. For all functionality tests, the medium pressure storage bank was used (4+5)

The main objective was to conduct functionality tests of the three setups with HD interfacing.

The NPL and Hy-SaM samplers were tested for flow metering against primary reference as the particulate sampler HYDAC PSA-H70. Setup is shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5 - HYDAC PSA-H70 tested with flow primary reference.

Comparison of sampling systems were made as well as repetition of tests.

The implementation of the three gaseous sampling systems was successfully achieved after careful planning (see Table 1, plan for the implementation of the gaseous sampling systems and Figures 5, 6, 7. 8) in October 2024. Note that HySAM was previously tested for functionality and thus not listed in table.

Description	Sampling system	Sampling type	Pressure line	Protocol	Pre-cooling	Manual pressure setting
Functionality test & comparison of systems	ENGIE	Direct	35 MPa HF	SAE J2601-1	T20 (HX)	SAE J2601-1
Functionality test & comparison of systems	NPL HD Direct	Direct	35 MPa HF	Maintenance	T20 (HX)	Manually set
Repetition	ENGIE	Direct	35 MPa HF	SAE J2601-1	T20 (HX)	SAE J2601-1

Repetition	NPL HD Direct	Direct	35 MPa HF	Maintenance	T20 (HX)	Manually set
Particulate sampling with flow reference	HYDAC PSA-H70	Parallel	70 MPa LF	SAE J2601-1	T20 (HX)	-

Table 1. Plan for the implementation of the gaseous sampling systems

Figure 6 - Implementation of the Hy-Sam Sampling device

The Hy-SaM sampling device, which uses a parallel sampling approach, was tested for functionality with a 35 MPa HD dispenser, with a fuel delivery temperature of -20°C, with the SAE J2601-1 protocol. The pressure ramp rate was set manually according to SAE J2601-1 (see Table 2).

Table D3 - H35-T20: CHSS Capacity Category A non-communications

H35-T20 CHSS Capacity Category A Non-Comm		APRR [MPa/min]	Target Pressure, P _{target} [MPa]										
			Initial Tank Pressure, P ₀ [MPa]										
			0,5	2	5	10	15	20	30	35	>35		
Ambient Temperature, T _{amb} [°C]	>50	no fueling	no fueling	no fueling	no fueling	no fueling	no fueling	no fueling	no fueling	no fueling	no fueling	no fueling	no fueling
	50	<1	no fueling	no fueling	no fueling	no fueling	no fueling	no fueling	no fueling	no fueling	no fueling	no fueling	no fueling
	45	2,3	40,6	40,4	40,2	39,7	39,3	38,8	37,6	36,7	no fueling	no fueling	
	40	3,6	40,6	40,4	40,2	39,8	39,4	38,9	37,8	36,7	no fueling	no fueling	
	35	3,9	40,5	40,4	40,2	39,8	39,4	39,0	37,8	36,7	no fueling	no fueling	
	30	5,0	40,1	40,0	39,8	39,4	38,9	38,5	37,1	35,9	no fueling	no fueling	
	25	6,2	39,8	39,7	39,4	39,0	38,5	38,0	36,4	no fueling	no fueling	no fueling	
	20	7,6	39,5	39,4	39,1	38,6	38,1	37,4	35,7	no fueling	no fueling	no fueling	
	10	10,2	38,9	38,7	38,4	37,8	37,1	36,4	34,2	no fueling	no fueling	no fueling	
	0	15,3	38,6	38,4	38,0	37,2	36,3	35,3	32,5	no fueling	no fueling	no fueling	
	-10	16,9	38,0	37,7	37,2	36,2	35,2	34,0	30,8	no fueling	no fueling	no fueling	
	-20	18,6	37,3	37,0	36,4	35,2	34,0	32,6	no fueling	no fueling	no fueling	no fueling	
	-30	20,3	36,7	36,3	35,6	34,2	32,8	31,2	no fueling	no fueling	no fueling	no fueling	
-40	22,1	36,9	36,5	35,7	34,3	32,8	31,2	no fueling	no fueling	no fueling	no fueling		
<-40	no fueling	no fueling	no fueling	no fueling	no fueling	no fueling	no fueling	no fueling	no fueling	no fueling	no fueling	no fueling	

Table 2. J2601 establishes prescriptive general-purpose high flow fueling protocols and process limits for hydrogen fueling of vehicles with compressed hydrogen storage system (CHSS)

Figure 7 - Implementation of the NPL Sampling device

The NPL HD sampling device, which uses a direct sampling approach, was tested for functionality with a 35 MPa HD dispenser, with a fuel delivery temperature of -20°C , in maintenance mode. The pressure was set manually.

Figure 8 - Implementation of the ENGIE sampling device

The ENGIE sampling device, which uses a direct sampling approach, was tested for functionality with a 35 MPa HD dispenser, with a fuel delivery temperature of -20°C , with the SAE J2601-5 protocol (see Table 3)

Table C3 - Communications fueling pressure limits - H35 Pressure Class

H35 MCF-HF-G		Communications Fueling Pressure Limit, P_{limit_comm} [MPa]							
		Initial Tank Pressure, $P_{initial}$ [MPa]							
		≤ 3	5	10	15	20	30	35	> 35
Ambient Temperature, T_{amb} [°C]	> 50	no fueling	no fueling	no fueling	no fueling	no fueling	no fueling	no fueling	no fueling
	50	43.75	42.6	42.4	42.2	41.9	41.1	40.5	no fueling
	45	43.75	42.7	42.4	42.1	41.7	40.7	39.8	no fueling
	40	43.75	42.6	42.2	41.8	41.3	40.1	39.1	no fueling
	35	43.75	42.6	42.2	41.8	41.2	40.0	39.1	no fueling
	30	43.75	42.5	42.1	41.5	40.9	39.6	38.6	no fueling
	25	43.75	42.4	41.9	41.3	40.6	39.2	no fueling	no fueling
	20	43.75	42.2	41.6	40.9	40.2	38.7	no fueling	no fueling
	10	43.75	41.9	41.2	40.4	39.6	37.9	no fueling	no fueling
	0	43.75	41.3	40.4	39.5	38.5	36.5	no fueling	no fueling
	-10	43.75	41.1	40.3	39.3	38.4	36.3	no fueling	no fueling
	-20	43.75	41.0	40.1	39.2	38.3	no fueling	no fueling	no fueling
	-30	43.75	40.9	40.0	39.1	38.1	no fueling	no fueling	no fueling
	-40	43.75	40.7	39.8	38.9	38.0	no fueling	no fueling	no fueling
< -40	no fueling	no fueling	no fueling	no fueling	no fueling	no fueling	no fueling	no fueling	

Table 3. MCF-HF-G table, taken from SAE J2601-5.

3.2 Implementation of the systems at Tyseley Energy Park, Birmingham

The HRS was chosen for particulate matter sampling because of its history of quantifiable amounts of particulate matter in dispensed fuel. H35 and H70 dispensers were available for sampling.

The Tyseley Refuelling Hub is the UK's first publicly accessible multi-fuel station offering low- and zero-carbon fuels. Opened in 2021, it is the UK's largest green hydrogen refuelling station. Powered by a dedicated offshore wind turbine, it produces CO2-free, fuel-cell-quality hydrogen. It includes a refuelling station for cars operating at 700 and 350 bar, two stations for buses at 350 bar and one for pipe trailers at up to 450 bar. It can produce over a tonne of hydrogen per day — enough to refuel up to 40 buses. At Tyseley, there were mainly buses refuelling. One FCEV was available for H70 sampling.

The implementation of the HYDAC PSA-H70 and the HYDAC PSA-H70 MCP 02 was successfully achieved after careful planning (see Figures 9 and 10) in February 2025.

Figure 9 - Implementation of the HYDAC PSA-H70 (SINTEF)

Figure 10 - Implementation of the HYDAC PSA-H70 MCP 02 (NPL) on the right and NPL ParSAM on the left.

The HYDAC systems were operated at reduced flow rate to avoid significant damage to the filter holder. The particulate samplings were realised during bus refuelling up to complete refill at 350 bar following amended filling protocol ensuring maximum set flow. The pressure range of the test covered 20 to 350 bar. The average flow rate was 15 – 25 g/s with maximum around 45g/s (Figure 11).

Figure 11 - Example of flow rate during HD particulate sampling

The use of HYDAC PSA-H70 and HYDAC PSA-H70 MCP 02 was achieved for heavy duty application under flow restricted conditions to ensure safety of the sampling assembly. Following the amended filling protocol, it was possible to realize particulate sampling during bus refueling. Further work is needed to enable particulate HD sampling at higher flow safely.

During the campaign at Tyseley Energy Park, Birmingham, the NPL ParSAM was implemented to take gas samples during bus refueling. The functionality test was carried out with a 35 MPa HD dispenser, with a fuel delivery temperature of ambient temperature, with an amended filling protocol (controlled filling by operator with reduced flow and pressure ramp). Further to the functionality test, the NPL ParSAM was implemented at another HD HRS for bus refueling using standard SAE J2601 fueling protocol.

During the exercise at Tyseley Energy Park, Birmingham, NPL PARsAM has been implemented in series with HYDAC PSA-H70 sampler to demonstrate the compatibility of the system to sample particulate and gas during one event.

4 Conclusions

The report describes summarily the hydrogen sampling strategies which have been developed in the task 2.1 (gaseous species) and 2.2 (particulates) of the project MetHyTrucks and the steps needed to implement these devices onsite (task 2.3). The report also shows the successful implementation of these devices at two different stations: at the ZBT station in Duisburg, Germany, October 2024 and at the Tyseley Refuelling Hub, UK in September 2025.

In this report, we consider only the implementation i.e. assessing the functionality of the sampling systems at a HD-HRS and compliance with the refuelling protocols and other HRS parameters. Safety and venting aspects, validation/comparison are discussed in other reports/deliverables.

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